

IMPACT OF LANGUAGE LEARNING RESOURCES ON ENGLISH PROFICIENCY OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN MINDANAO STATE UNIVERSITY - SULU

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to understand the impact of language learning resources on English proficiency of senior high school students in MSU-Sulu. The study utilized qualitative research design through descriptive method. The data were collected through open-ended interviews with committed educators. In addition, six MSU-Sulu Senior High School dedicated English teachers were selected as the participants of this study. The research identified a range of resources at the school including traditional materials such as textbooks and dictionaries and technological resources like online platforms and mobile apps. The result shows that utilizing a variety of these resources effectively improved students' English proficiency. This included enhanced vocabulary, better comprehension skills, and increased fluency. It is also revealed that these resources have indispensable role in molding not only students' learning as well as the teaching style and enthusiasm of the MSU-Sulu teachers. Challenges faced by teachers in utilizing these resources were also highlighted in this study. The study also explored the strategies employed by teachers to overcome these challenges and to effectively incorporate these resources into their teaching. This study also recommends conducting a comprehensive inventory and assessment of the current language learning resources, implementing regular surveys or feedback methods to assess the perceived impact of language learning resources, addressing the stated challenges that English language teachers encounter while accessing and utilizing language learning resources, encouraging English language teachers to collaborate and share expertise. Lastly, future researchers doing a similar study are encouraged to include both students and teachers as participants and may consider utilizing quantitative analysis as their approach.

Keywords: *Language Learning Resources, English Proficiency, Mindanao State University-Sulu, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

English proficiency has become critical in unlocking both professional and personal prospects in today's linked world. With the increasing globalization and interconnectedness of the world, the ability to communicate effectively in English has become a valuable skill not just for students but for every individual in the world. Mastering English is not only beneficial for academic success, it also opens doors to a world of opportunities in various fields and also essential for international communication. In fact, Santos et al., (2022) stated that the Philippines recognizes English as one of its official languages. All individuals must be fluent in both written and spoken English. (Eslit & Valderama, 2023). This will allow for more transparent and effective communication.

Language learning resources such as books, online resources, technologies and other resources have a significant role in enhancing everyone's English proficiency. According to Sari et al. (2022), e-books assist develop not only communication and collaborative skills, but also critical problem-solving abilities. Park and Lee (2021) recommend that teachers should encourage young students to continue reading printed books in order to strengthen their in-depth reading comprehension and grammar skills. The study of Macancela (2019) also points out that websites make a significant contribution to English language learning by helping teachers employ dynamic strategies that make it easier to reinforce the cognitive approach. Assessing the effectivity of various language learning resources is essential, ranging from conventional textbooks to smartphone apps and internet platforms. It can determine which resources are most beneficial in improving English proficiency.

English teachers choose a variety of materials to keep their students engaged, challenged, and ultimately equipped to become self-assured communicators. Prwati et al., (2019) stated that Learning resources have many different applications in the teaching-learning process. Making the best use of educational materials can support both teachers and students in the process of teaching and learning. The growing diversity of language learning resources, including textbooks, online platforms and technologies provide numerous opportunities to enrich language instruction. However, along with the benefits, English teachers face obstacles in effectively integrating these resources into their teaching. As stated by Johnson et al., (2016), although most teachers recognize the advantages of educational technologies, they often find it challenging to integrate new tools into their lessons in a seamless and efficient manner. Every level of school system faces substantial obstacles when it comes to technology integration, from the accession of new technological equipments to the modification of curricula and teaching methods to accommodate new educational resources.

For MSU-Sulu senior high school students, not having access to certain resources, particularly those that mostly rely on technology can pose some challenges in their learning.

Lack of resources might result in students not receiving a proper education and can be very difficult for teachers. It could lead to a decrease in enrollment.

This study will examine the availability of these resources for use in educational settings and explore strategies for bridging the digital divide between digital resources and traditional materials such as locally accessible websites and textbooks. Additionally, investigating English teachers' preferred learning styles and resource accessibility can inform initiatives to address resource disparities and ensure equitable access to quality language learning opportunities.

The study's significance from its potential to improve students' academic performance and English proficiency. It attempts to improve students' academic performance by identifying efficient language learning tools and methods catered to their linguistic backgrounds. As a means of developing students' language proficiency as well as their appreciation of the diversity of the English language and cross-cultural understanding. Faculty members may also improve the educational system to better prepare students for their future academic and professional endeavors by using the study's practical findings to inform curriculum design and resource allocation. Informed professional development programs can enable educators to become more proficient language learning facilitators by recognizing how teachers function as curators and catalysts in optimizing the impact of resources. This study also offers future researchers a starting point to investigate sociolinguistic effects on language learning in various settings, including MSU-Sulu.

Research Questions

This study seeks to find out the impact of language learning resources on the English proficiency of senior high school students in MSU-Sulu, focusing on the perspectives and experiences of MSU teachers as key participants.

Specifically, this study seeks answers to the following questions:

1. What language learning resources are available in MSU-Sulu senior high school for improving English proficiency?
2. What are the impact of language learning resources on the English proficiency of senior high school students in MSU-Sulu as perceived by English language teachers?
3. What are the challenges faced by English language teachers in accessing and utilizing language learning resources for English language education in MSU-Sulu Senior High School?
4. What are the strategies employed by English language teachers in utilizing language learning resources to enhance the English proficiency of senior high school students in MSU-Sulu?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School, Philippines. The mentioned high school is in Capitol Site, Jolo Sulu and was established in 2016. It has two buildings. The first, or main building, can be found near the campus gymnasium, while the second, which is considered its administration building, is situated between the College of Agriculture and the College of Arts and Sciences. In addition, it offers three (3) strands: General Academic Strand (GAS), Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMMS), and Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM).

Sampling Method

The researchers selected a purposive of six senior high school English teachers that are currently working at MSU-Sulu to serve as participants in this study. Their perspectives from years of influencing young brains, were invaluable. Participants were recruited through voluntary participation and informed consent.

In this study, the researchers used Purposive Sampling or Judgement sampling to select the participant of the study. According to Crossman (2020), as cited by Jailani et al. (2024), Sasapan et. al. (2024), Basir et. al. (2024) and Sabbaha et. al. (2024) Purposive Sampling is a non-probability sample that is selected based on characteristics of a population and the objective of the study.

Research Instrument

The main instrument used in conducting this study was a self-developed questionnaire which consists of open-ended questions. The focus of this research was open-ended interviews with dedicated teachers to investigate the impact of language learning resources on the English proficiency of senior high school students at MSU-Sulu. The researchers explored their findings on the usefulness of current tools, the problems in utilizing these resources, and their suggestions for optimizing the learning environment through open-ended conversations. In addition, Züll, (2016) defined open-ended survey questions as any questions that do not have an established list of possible answers. When answering open-ended questions, participants must come up with an original response that they can express verbally or in writing.

Data Gathering Procedure

Furthermore, before distributing the survey questionnaires, the researchers checked that all study participants gave their consent.

For the procedure of collecting data, the researchers asked permission from the director of MSU-Sulu senior high school to allow them to conduct their study. The researchers then secured a written permit. Afterward, the researchers gave a letter to each target participants to ask for their permission and cooperation for the launching of the questionnaire consisting open-ended questions for initiating the interviews. The researchers then deployed the survey questionnaire and retrieved it the day after, for participants to have enough time answering it. Lastly, the researchers compiled and analyzed the data that was provided by the participants.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the data gathered from the participants of this study are coded, analyzed and categorized into themes to further understand the impact of language learning resources on English proficiency of senior high school students in MSU-Sulu.

3.1 Language Learning Resources available in MSU-Sulu Senior High School.

Language learning resources covers a wide range of materials including books, online resources, technologies and other resources that could help not just students but everyone to learn and improve their English proficiency. Books have long been staple resources for students, they continue to play an important role in language acquisition. Park and Lee (2021) recommended that teachers should encourage young students to continue reading printed books in order strengthen their in-depth reading comprehension and grammar skills. Online resources such as websites, apps and platforms have revolutionized the way people learn languages. Wang et al., (2023) stated in their study that the internet is a valuable resource in a culture that has advanced technologically, and the study found out that the internet significantly impacts academic self-efficacy and the process of learning English. Language learning technologies such as information and communication technologies (ICT) and educational technologies (EdTech) have also expanded the opportunities for immersive practice and feedback. These resources can assist learners in honing their English proficiency such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing ability. According to Huda (2023), the widespread use of the internet and the development of technology have completely changed the way that people learn, allowing learners to acquire knowledge in new ways.

Available language learning resources. According to the participants' narrative, English teachers of MSU-Sulu senior high school utilizes a mix of traditional and technological resources in their instruction. This includes materials like books, modules, dictionaries, and visual aids, alongside online resources like videos, mobile apps, and projector presentations. Notably, the recent implementation of free university-wide internet by MSU-Sulu has made accessing online resources significantly easier for students compared to previous years. The result of Andreyeva et al., (2019) research showed that, in comparison to traditional teaching approaches, the use of computer technology in the process of teaching foreign languages provides for better results in practically all language elements and types of speech activity. However, Guarino et al., (2014) emphasized in their study that the internet can be a useful tool in meeting their educational needs but textbooks remained as students' preferred resource. Thus, teaching English can be done through both conventional and technological methods.

I usually use books, modules, dictionaries for vocabulary building, worksheets, instructional or online videos, class activities or group activities such as, presentation (speaking, writing, and reading activities) in teaching (P1, Excerpt 1).

The available language learning resources used in MSU-Sulu SHS preferably were modules, also by means of video/video presentation to be shown in the projector, others may use flashcards, project supplies and visual

aids (P2, Excerpt 2).

The only available language learning resources in MSU-Sulu are Textbooks, Mobile App, Language Learning books, and Language Learning websites (P4, Excerpt 3).

Based on what I have experienced during this semester, there are various language learning resources available in MSU-Sulu Senior High School such as books and as well as online resources since MSU-Sulu provides free internet (P5, Excerpt 4).

As language learning requires ample resources, they include the use of multimedia resources as learning materials. Though not limited to, the use of today's technological advances has vastly impacts the educational scenario. Credible sites such as google scholar.com brottanica.com and other learning resources are some I personally use as well other than the modules prescribed by the DepEd (P6 Excerpt 5).

Frequently used language learning resources. With regards to the frequently used resources when teaching English to the students, it is said that modules, textbooks, mobile apps, and online resources are used more often by the English teachers at MSU-Sulu senior high school. This finding from Park and Lee (2021) is directly relevant to the results about the language learning resources available at MSU-Sulu senior high school. The results indicate that teachers primarily utilize a combination of traditional and technological resources, including textbooks and modules, which can be considered forms of “printed books” in the context of this study.

Moreover, some of them rely more heavily on technological advancements as sources, as they can assist them in grasping and seeking more information and comprehensive texts, particularly in the field of English language learning education. Additionally, Macancela (2019) emphasized the importance of technological tools such as website in the variety of interactive activities and practices for understanding the English language, and improving the motivation of students in the improvement of the activities of the subject.

I frequently use textbooks or modules, worksheets or activity sheets and class activities (P1 Excerpt 6).

I personally used modules, wherein ahead of time given to them, so that they may have something to read, background of the subject or ideas to be studied (P2, Excerpt 7).

Basically I only used textbooks, mobile app, and language learning websites (P4, Excerpt 8).

I usually use online resources, to seek for more comprehensive texts especially in the field of language teaching (P5, Excerpt 9).

As I have mentioned, I heavily rely on the technological advances, as to take advantage of its proliferance modules, research materials and other studies related to my topics are all integrated as my sources in which I use for instruction (P6, Excerpt 10).

Helpful language learning resources for teaching English. Based on the teachers' statements, not all of the available resources are helpful, and some of them may also be unhelpful in teaching. According to the participants, the resources that are helpful to them are textbooks, mobile apps, video presentations, and online resources. On the other hand, one of them stated that visual aids are unhelpful because students don't really pay attention to what is written there.

The most helpful one is the video presentation, subject to be shown in the projector, it really helps students visualize and understand deeply the discussion. The unhelpful one I think is the visual aids, they do not pay attention of what is written there (P2, Excerpt 11).

To be honest, all of the resources that can be found in MSU-Sulu SHS, such as books, e-books, e-paf and such are very helpful in terms of acquiring knowledge and effectively delivering it to the students (P5, Excerpt 12).

As mentioned, websites carrying various disciplines are integral for me as I facilitate the learning of my students. So far, studies I find on Google scholar.com and the modules from DepEd are my top reliable resources (P6, Excerpt 13).

3.2. Impact of Language Learning Resources on English Proficiency of Senior High School Students in MSU-Sulu.

The use of language learning resources has a significant impact in both teaching and learning English. Hassan (2014) mentioned that most individuals believed that without any learning materials, learning a language in an academic environment is impossible. Integrating language learning resources in teaching also allows students to enhance their English proficiency such as speaking, reading, and writing, and their confidence and motivation to engage with the English language. For MSU-Sulu teachers, having access to language learning resources such as books, online resources, and technologies also allows them to create effective and immersive learning environments. By utilizing these resources, MSU-Sulu teachers can further improve their English teaching process, ultimately leading to improved English skills of students.

Impact of language learning resources on students' English proficiency. The responses provided by English teachers offer a diverse perspective on the impact of language learning resources on senior high school students' English proficiency at MSU-Sulu. The teachers acknowledge the varied preferences among students, highlighting the importance of adapting resources to cater to individual learning styles. Several teachers emphasize the positive impact of different resource types, such as worksheets and mobile apps, in enhancing students' speaking, reading, and writing skills. Clear instructional purposes are noted as crucial for effective learning. One teacher, however, exclusively relies on modules, emphasizing their role in expanding students' English vocabulary in writing. Experience plays a significant role, as one teacher with over nine years of service stresses the importance of students' willingness to exert effort for effective learning. Electronic means, as mentioned by another teacher, are recognized for their accessibility and contribution to English proficiency, especially in the early stages of lecturing. In the study of Alghamdi et al.

(2019), stated that incorporating authentic tasks and resources into English language instruction can improve students' speaking fluency and equip them with the skills they need to communicate effectively outside of the classroom.

The impact of the different types of resources may vary depending on how students respond to each types. There are many students who find it hard to learn language proficiency through having on the spot activity rather find themselves engaged in having worksheets are activity sheets where they can really express themselves on their own (P1, Excerpt 14).

Through these different types of resources used, it has really good and strong impact to the students' English proficiency such as speaking, reading, and writing where it established clear instructional purposes. In their speaking, it makes positive connections to others where they can comfortably share their ideas, feelings and experience. In reading they could actually comprehend well and visualize it. Lastly, writing- through this, it could support and assess the so called (HOTS) preferably the overall critical thinking and analysis that they have undergone through the said resources (P2, Excerpt 15).

Since I only use module, base from their activities some students have widen their vocabulary in English in terms of writing (P3, Excerpt 16).

I strongly believe, that learning depends on the capacity of the students to learn. I believe they learn when they eagerly exert effort. Base on the experience, in more than 9 years in service and in teaching, all of these resources are helpful when they properly instructed on how to use and how they should apply for instance the Mobile App (P4, Excerpt 17).

Among all the types of resources that I use, the ones given by the DepEd has given me far more favorable results from my class (P6, Excerpt 18).

Utilization of language learning resources enhanced students' confidence and motivation to engage with the English language. The participants of this study collectively illustrate their belief in the importance of English proficiency and the positive impact of language learning resources on students' confidence and motivation. They highlight the role of these resources in helping students reach the fluency level of their peers and the effectiveness of engaging in school activities like speech or English clubs. There's an emphasis on the enthusiasm and self-directed learning of students, as well as the increasing engagement observed throughout the semester, particularly through internet-based language learning. Additionally, one of the participants underscores the complex nature of teaching instruction and the role of language resources in enhancing teaching methods. Overall, it emphasizes the transformative effect of language resources on students' language proficiency journeys. Yokubjonova et al. (2022) stated that reading English-language books has been highlighted as a crucial component of language acquisition, fostering the growth of vocabulary, grammar, and critical thinking abilities. These studies collectively suggest that reading books, especially literature, can have a significant and positive impact on the development of English language skills and proficiency.

I believe that being able to use English as a language is a must and what I have noticed in my class with the execution of the language learning resources

help them unleash the capacity to be at par with those who are fluent and proficient in English. Their motivation and confidence has improved and this can be a great indicator of their progress in their language learning proficiency journey (P1 Excerpt 19).

I could probably say that if they had really enhanced the so called used of language resources by means of engaging different school activities both inside and outside the class for example joining clubs like speech club, English club where it promotes and boosts students' confidence and motivation (P2 Excerpt 20).

I believe students with great enthusiasm and interests will definitely learn not only with the guidance of the teachers, rather even in their own little way (P4 Excerpt 21).

I can see that as we go along with our class for this semester, they are really becoming more engaged through language learning when it is from the internet (P5, Excerpt 22).

I believe that the use of language learning resources has enhanced my students' confidence and motivation to engage with the English language because this embodies a much more complex method of research, relearning and perfecting the profession of teaching instruction as a teacher (P6, Excerpt 23).

Utilization of language learning resources in teaching help teachers improve their way of teaching English. Based on the participants' statements, language learning resources did not just helped students to improve their English proficiency but also helped teachers like them in many ways. Their statements expressed gratitude and appreciation for how these resources helped them improve their way of teaching, as well as, their passion in their profession. It became clear that the participants recognized the indispensable role of language learning resources in shaping not only their students' learnings but also their own evolution as dedicated teachers. Teachers' resourcefulness is essential since the appropriate and effective use of all existing resources is critical to the development of any educational system or organization. Resources are crucial to education and to instructors in particular since they can help to advance both their personal and professional growth (Chigeza, 2022).

As a teacher, the application of language learning resources does not only limit to students. Along with the execution of these language learning resources, I have also noticed that, these made me, if not good or fluent or proficient, at least able to handle my class discussions with its proper and sufficient execution (P1, Excerpt 24).

It usually means a lot and helpful for us, as a teacher, engaging and using different types of language learning resources could have a very big impact, we also learned and studied. Thus, facing and engaging students is but a challenge. We may encounter from time to time, so we really see to it, that we must prepared enough. And the so called mastering, in facing our energetic students, to prevent any circumstances, for instance, lackness of skills in establishing clear discussions (P2, Excerpt 25).

I have a lot of personal achievement in terms of how the language

learning resources had helped me improve my way of teaching English. I could barely remember how I manage to come up with a standardized pronunciation and literally speak spontaneously (P4, Excerpt 26).

As a teacher, it is way more effective to impart knowledge by using any language learning resources that you can use, I have improved it through these resources because it makes me confident in facing the students (P5, Excerpt 27).

As a teacher, and most significantly a lifelong learner, the use of resources for learning are what I deem necessary to comprehensively be more dependent on. Arrogance has no space in the field of education (P6, Excerpt 28).

3.3 Challenges Faced by English Language Teachers in Accessing and Utilizing Language Learning Resources for English Language Education in MSU-Sulu Senior High School.

Students' use of language learning resources profoundly impacts their English language education. Understanding the challenges English teachers face in accessing and utilizing resources at MSU-Sulu Senior High School allows for the development of more effective and tailored teaching strategies. The study of Agung (2019) demonstrates the various challenges that English teachers face in teaching English language. These challenges include the poor level of language comprehension among the students, limited resources of materials, the communication gap that exists between the lecturers and the students, the students' lack of interest and engagement in the classroom, and the absence of social and environmental support.

Main Barriers and Obstacles that the Teachers Encounter in Utilizing Language Resources. The interviews revealed that students' anxiety can hinder participation in recitations, discussions, and other learning activities. According to Sadighi (2017) anxiety related to learning a foreign language is one of the affective factors that has a negative impact on language acquisition. Noise from neighboring classrooms is also highlighted as main obstacle for it disrupts lessons and makes it difficult for students to learn effectively. Cheryan et al., (2014) points out in their study that learning is significantly impacted by a building's structural features. Furthermore, there is a strong correlation between lower student achievement and poor lighting, noise, poor air quality, and inadequate heating in the classroom.

Participant 6 revealed that language barrier is also one of the obstacles teachers faced in effectively teaching English. Students with limited English proficiency may struggle to understand the learning resources. According to Ashikuzzaman (2023), Language barriers in the classroom have the potential to seriously impair participation, interrupt the flow of information, and restrict meaningful interactions between teachers and students.

These responses showcase the importance of considering various factors beyond the resources themselves. Effective language learning requires addressing student anxiety, adapting to classroom environments, and bridging language barriers.

One obstacles and barriers that I usually encountered in my class during recitations and discussion is the level of students anxiety, even not in speaking but on the entirety of the learning process, for if the students find it hard to learn speaking, reading, and writing and other activities will be affected too (P1, Excerpt 29).

In my own experience, the main barriers and obstacles that I encountered in utilizing language learning resources in my teaching is “physical noise”, perhaps our classrooms are usually close enough to one another, it is really hard for me to compete with voice coming from the other room (P2, Excerpt 30).

Language barrier is one of the main barriers or obstacles that I faced in integrating these resources in my teaching. Not all learners can comprehend the English language, as much as the others could (P6, Excerpt 31).

Students’ behavior affecting the teachers’ utilization of language learning resources. Students’ behavior is a two-way street when it comes to language learning resources. As Participant 2 points out, disruptive behavior throws a wrench in a teacher's ability to use resources effectively. It's hard to concentrate on implementing a lesson plan when you're constantly managing the classroom. Khasinah (2017) defined disruptive behavior of students as students’ misbehavior or poor involvement in class. Such behaviors frequently cause disruptions to the teaching and learning process in the classroom since these actions have an impact on both teachers and other students as well. On the other hand, Participant 6 suggests that student behavior can also be a signal of their interest. Disengaged students might be acting out because the chosen resources aren't engaging them. In both cases, understanding the reasons behind students’ behaviors allows teachers to adapt their approach and resource selection. This can lead to a more productive learning environment where students are actively involved and teachers can effectively utilize the resources at their disposal. Moreover, it is essential for teachers to stimulate their student’s enthusiasm for learning the English language. (Amjah, 2013).

Yes, it really affects my utilization of language learning resources especially in my teaching. I can’t concentrate well, because all the time I keep my eyes watching on them and always reminding them to be behave, not just me, as well as their classmates will be affected, so the tendency is there will no learning at all (P2, Excerpt 32).

Definitely. Because the learners’ behaviors are a reflection of how well they are interested in the class (P2, Excerpt 33).

Supports and professional development that the teachers need to effectively integrate language learning resources into their teaching. In accordance with the participants’ assertion, there are various form of support and professional development that they need in order for them to effectively teach English to their students. These includes the access to workshops and seminars for integrating language learning resources, interaction with influential and inspiring individuals to support mental well-being and professional growth, opportunities for further education such as educational courses and masteral degrees to enhance teaching skill, regular and rigorous remedial classes and constant drills to support

student performance, especially in language, peer support and interaction with co-teachers for collaborative learning and development, self-motivation, and support from superiors, as well as, the encouragement from peers to navigate the challenges of the teaching profession. Additionally, Sancar et al., (2021) stated that developing teachers professionally is essential to raising student achievement. Furthermore, their varied form of support and needs from dynamic nature of their profession encompasses not only professional development but also the well-being, educational advancement and progress of the students.

For professional development, it is with great privileged to attend workshops and seminars on the integration of language learning resources (P1, Excerpt 34).

I think the kind of support that I am longing for and could help my professional development is to be with good influential people. I think this means a lot for me, verily if you were being surrounded good people that will always remind and inspired you to work harder and love your profession, you will be inspired to go to school. I mean for me mental health is very important, thus if this will be affected it loosen your capability to control emotion (P2, Excerpt 35).

It is always a must to fully understand what you are teaching and master your topics. This is through taking educational courses and masteral degrees (P3, Excerpt 36).

I believe a regular and a rigorous remedial class can be of by helps in order to give way to these students with their performance especially in language. Constant drills is highly recommended too (P4, Excerpt 37).

Maybe in terms of peer support from my co-teachers, I hope I can interact with them more (P5, Excerpt 38).

The kind of support that we need as teachers come from our own selves. The teaching profession is challenging, and self-motivation as a professional is important. Also supports from our superiors at work and peers is important (P6, Excerpt 39).

3.4 Strategies Employed by English Language Teachers in Utilizing Language Learning Resources to Enhance the English Proficiency of Senior High School Students in MSU-Sulu.

Having effective strategies for teaching the English language is crucial and essential. English has become the primary medium of communication in the global community, making it important to provide proper focus and methods for its instruction. Creating an immersive language learning environment, including technology, realistic materials, offering regular feedback, and encouraging extracurricular language practice are all successful techniques for helping students improve their English language skills. By using these tactics, instructors can help students become confident and effective English language users, providing them with a valuable asset that will open doors to a globalized world. (Budiman et al., 2023). In the pursuit of enhancing English proficiency among senior high school students at MSU-Sulu, English language teachers employ a variety of strategies to effectively utilize language learning resources. These strategies are designed to create an engaging and immersive

learning environment that fosters language acquisition and proficiency. By understanding the specific needs and learning styles of their students, teachers at MSU-Sulu implement tailored approaches that harness language learning resources to optimize the English language learning experience. Additionally, this manner sets the stage for an exploration of the diverse and impactful strategies employed by English language teachers to elevate the English proficiency of senior high school students within the unique context of MSU-Sulu.

Teaching strategies and methods that the teachers employed to help students enhance their English proficiency. Based on the participants' statements, it appears that they are implementing a structured strategic approach to classroom activities. The sequence of group discussions, partner group reporting, and word recitation suggests an interactive and collaborative learning environment. Additionally, the English language teachers' strategy focuses on engaging students in reporting and facilitating discussions, indicating a commitment to ensuring understanding and clarity for the students. Discussion and reporting have been identified as an effective approach to foster a better learning environment and habit of collaborative problem-solving, which helps participant students develop research ideas and skills in various educational contexts especially in English language (Dancis et al., 2023). Additionally, participant 3 stated that he/she used the grammar translation method, which focuses on translating between the target language and the native language, and also the incorporate elements of the direct method into his/her teaching approach. These strategies technically help students understand the structure and grammar of the target language, as well as develop their translation, speaking and listening skills, promoting fluency and natural language use. Moreover, a grammar translation method is currently one of the effective means of building foreign language competences in English (Ishchenko et al., 2022).

To help students grasp complex concepts, learn from each other and develop important social and communication skills, enhance their understanding and retention of the material, and develop their language proficiency and skills, both participants 4 and 6 employed the direct instruction or method, which prioritize unconstrained communication in teaching, aiming to benefit both teachers and students. Furthermore, direct instruction is one of the most widely used teacher-centered methodologies and has proven effectiveness in providing information and developing step-by-step skills. Its central purpose is promoting student on-task behavior through explicit instruction, ongoing support, and student engagement in successful practice, being focused on the interaction between teachers and students. (Guzmán, 2020).

In addition, participant 4 mentioned that the usage of the audio-lingual method and communicative language teaching method is beneficial. Nita and Syafei (2012) also concluded that audio-lingual method and communicative language teaching are useful and applicable in teaching speaking skills.

I prepare group discussions, partner group reporting, and word recitation as my teaching strategies (P1, Excerpt 40).

As of now, since my subject is Reading Writing Skills I see to it, I engage my students in reporting. Everyone are subject to report, also we have a brief discussion right after reporting, I'm going to make sure, there will be no doubts and clarifications left. In terms in writing, I give them activity assignment to be

done at home. (P2, Excerpt 41).

I simply use grammar translation method and with the collaboration of direct method (P3, Excerpt 42).

Direct instruction, lecture, cooperative learning, and experiential learning are the best strategies and the direct method. Audio-lingual method and communicative language teaching method are the best method. Each of these has its own strengths and weaknesses (P4, Excerpt 43).

Direct method, I believe that teaching without constraint in communication serve both the teachers and students well (P6, Excerpt 44).

Integrating technologies to support English teaching. The participants emphasize the potential of technology, particularly cellphones and apps, to enhance English proficiency among students. They highlight the importance of leveraging technology for educational purposes. For instance, using the internet for research and assignments, as well as utilizing apps for pronunciation practice and incorporating video presentations for interactive role plays. They also encourage students to embrace technology as a tool for educational advancement and language learning, recognizing its ability to engage and empower students in their English language development. According to Speck (2019), English language learners will benefit if they approach technology. Smart phone technology will use the benefits of studying, enhancing, rehearsing, and developing speaking skills.

I guess everyone has their own access to the internet by means of cellphone, through that, they could actually search deeply and to have a better and clear understanding towards English proficiency.

Giving them assignment from time to time so that they could not just used their cellphone for entertainment but for as well, educational purposes (P2, Excerpt 45).

I always ask my students to use technology in order to enhance and further their knowledge. For instance, I will ask them to use an app to check if the pronunciation for a certain word is correct or not. In making a role play, I used to ask them to provide it with video presentation (P4, Excerpt 46).

Modifying the use of resources in teaching English according to the different learning needs and language backgrounds of the students. In conformity with the participants' narrative, they indicated the importance of relating the resources they utilize and the lesson content to the students' backgrounds and experiences. They emphasize the significance of understanding students' comprehension levels and language backgrounds, as well as the necessity of adjusting teaching methods and resources accordingly. Additionally, participant 2 highlights the value of thorough lesson planning, assessing students' understanding, and ensuring that lessons are effectively delivered. Moreover, their combined approaches and strategies underscore how they modify the use of resources in teaching English according to the different learning needs and language backgrounds of students. Furthermore, Raza (2018) stated that teachers must fulfill each student's learning needs in a classroom with varying levels of language proficiency by using strategies that will benefit all students.

Modification of each resources has something to do with students' level

of understanding. I for one, if I noticed that my students were not able to cope up with lesson discussed, I did some adjustments on my way of teaching. I ensure that student were provided with each learning resources base on their need and language background (P1, Excerpt 47).

Well for me, I'm going to make sure that planning lessons must secured first, of course understanding the status of your students lastly having an "assessment" right after discussions and the rest is history (P2, Excerpt 48).

Sometimes, I actually relate the learning resources to their rationality, and such, I use examples like how would they be if they were the people in the stories (P5, Excerpt 49).

Conclusions

This study investigated the impact of language learning resources on the English proficiency of MSU-Sulu senior high school students. Through interviews with English teachers, the research identified a range of resources available at the school. These included traditional materials like books and dictionaries, alongside technological resources like online platforms and mobile apps. The study revealed that utilizing a variety of these resources effectively improved students' English proficiency. This included enhanced vocabulary, better comprehension skills, and increased fluency. Additionally, the teachers themselves reported a positive impact on their teaching styles and enthusiasm.

However, the research also highlighted challenges faced by teachers in utilizing these resources. Limited access to resources, a lack of training on integrating them, and a shortage of classroom facilities were some of the key obstacles. Interestingly, the study also found that student factors like anxiety levels and disruptive behavior could affect resource effectiveness. These challenges emphasize the need for solutions to maximize the potential of language learning resources and optimize the learning experience for MSU-Sulu students.

The study explored strategies employed by teachers to overcome these challenges and to effectively utilize language learning resources in enhancing students' English proficiency. These included implementing structured activities, creating interactive learning environments, and integrating technology into assessments. Notably, teachers reported using a mix of methods like the audio-lingual method and communicative language teaching to enhance student engagement.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this qualitative study on the impact of language learning resources on English proficiency of senior high school students in MSU-Sulu, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Resource Assessment. Conduct a comprehensive inventory and assessment of the current language learning resources in MSU-Sulu senior high school to identify gaps and areas for improvement. This could involve working with teachers, administrators, and

students to gain insights into the efficacy and usefulness of present resources. Umar (2018) stated that assessment for learning involves frequent, interactive assessments of students' progress and knowledge to detect learning difficulties and tailor education to individual needs. A comprehensive analysis of his research demonstrates that this style of assessment is very successful at improving students' academic performance and enthusiasm to learn.

2. Proficiency Feedback. Implement regular surveys or feedback methods to assess the perceived impact of language learning resources on the English proficiency of senior high school students. Engage English language teachers in reflective discussions to better understand their observations and recommendations for improving the effectiveness of these resources. In the study of Al-Bashir et al. (2016), stated that individualised written feedback can be useful in assisting students to learn. However, the process is time consuming. If there are a large number of students, it places additional strain on teachers' time to produce these remarks.

3. Teacher Support. Address the stated challenges that English language teachers encounter while accessing and utilizing language learning resources. This could include offering professional development opportunities, assigning adequate funding for resource engagement, and building support networks to assist instructors in overcoming technological or administrative obstacles. An et al. (2022), their research found that perceived teacher support is substantially related to learning engagement. Learning motivation mediates the relationship between perceived teacher support and learning engagement.

4. Collaboration Workshops. Encourage English language teachers to collaborate and share expertise in order to exchange best practices and strategies for efficiently utilizing language learning resources. Create forums or workshops where teachers can share successful ideas and learn from one another's experiences, thereby improving the English proficiency of senior high school students in MSU-Sulu. Burton (2015)'s qualitative study found that effective teacher collaboration includes shared or common goals, teacher efficacy, and positive interdependence among teachers. Other related themes arose, including successful collaboration activities that improve the learning environment.

5. Inclusive Research. Future researchers doing a similar study are encouraged to include both students and teachers as participants. Researchers can acquire a comprehensive picture of the impact of language learning resources by merging student viewpoints and English proficiency data into quantitative analysis. This technique not only adds to the study data, but it also provides useful insights into students' experiences and learning outcomes, allowing for a more comprehensive evaluation of the effectiveness of language learning resources in improving English proficiency. According to Nayman and Altun's (2021) research, teachers' and students' perspectives on learning and teaching are compatible under a basic framework that includes self-study, student involvement, active lesson process, teaching the lesson as art, and, most importantly, the importance of reading habits.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers followed the research ethics protocol listed below throughout the research process.

Protection from bodily and psychological harm. The researcher ensured that the study's participants were not subjected to embarrassment, insult, harassment, injury, or any

other type of distress. Instead, the researchers maintained the individuals' physical and psychological safety.

Confidentiality of the collected data. The researchers also made sure that the participants' personal information and other data obtained were kept anonymous and strictly confidential unless they provide their full approval.

Absence of deception. The researchers ensured that there was no deception involved in the process of the study. All participants were informed about the study's objective, how the results were used, any potential negative effects of their participation, and who will have access to the results. Furthermore, before distributing the survey questionnaires, the researchers checked that all study participants gave their consent.

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